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All About China? (Mis)Reading Domestic Politics through a Great Power Lens

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Combining international relations and critical geopolitics literature with a public opinion survey in Thailand that delves into some rarely explored and sensitive questions to understand respondents' political views and attitudes, we examine the extent to which domestic political developments can be understood through a United States–China great power lens. Are politically progressive Thais more likely to be pro-US, and more politically conservative Thais likely to favor China? While we find some relationship between liberal domestic political leanings and sympathy for the United States, we also show that conservative domestic political leanings do not automatically translate into support for China. To view election outcomes in a country such as Thailand as “wins” for one or other great power would be highly misleading.

Key words: China, United States, Great Powers, domestic politics, Thailand

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When ISEAS-Yusof Institute published its annual survey of Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) opinion-leaders in April 2024 (Seah et al 2024), American news headlines were quick to seize on the answer to just one question. “China Topples US as SE Asia’s Favored Partner”, announced Bloomberg (Heijmans 2024), while CNBC declared: “U.S Loses its Spot to China as Southeast Asia’s Most Favored Ally” (Chiang 2024). Radio Free Asia ran the story under the headline “ASEAN is now more pro-China than U.S: Survey” (Radio Free Asia 2024). A few months earlier, the Council on Foreign Relations had opined that “The U.S is losing Ground to China in Southeast Asia” (Kurlantzick 2023). Headlines such as these are increasingly common when it comes to assessments of foreign policy attitudes and political developments in Southeast Asia. They are reflective of broader trends in Western geopolitical thinking, visible particularly among American journalists, foreign policy and defense practitioners, that signal the return of great power competition as the dominant foreign policy paradigm (Koch 2019, 911). Put simply, these commentators often view Southeast Asia as caught in a zero-sum game between two great powers, the United States and China. This is despite the fact that just 50.5 per cent of the 1994 respondents favored China in the ISEAS survey question that generated such excited global headlines – a tiny margin.

Besides shaping the collective understanding of international politics in the Western policy and journalistic circles, the great power lens is also increasingly coloring Western perceptions of domestic political developments in regions of key geostrategic importance to China and the United States. This is especially visible in China’s immediate neighborhood, notably in Southeast Asia (Gerstl 2023, 210-12; Strangio 2020, 10-11). The 1990s heyday of the third wave of democracy has long passed (Huntington 1991), and much recent academic debate about Southeast Asian politics concerns parsing the most appropriate frameworks and terminologies to explain hybrid regimes that mix democratic and authoritarian elements, in countries ranging from Cambodia to the Philippines. Democratic rollback and autocratic deepening, featuring promissory coups, executive aggrandizement, and electoral manipulation, have often been the order of the day (Bermeo 2016; Croissant and Lorenz 2018). Many scholars see China as an enabler of these trends by providing uninterrupted capital inflows and tacit support for increasingly authoritarian Southeast Asian elites, often at the expense of the West and its more values-driven approach to foreign policy and development in the post-Cold War world (Loughlin 2021; Einzerberger and Schaffar 2018; Rosser 2020, 306). In policy and journalistic circles, it has thus become extremely common to frame episodes of democratic backsliding and autocratic deepening across Southeast Asia through the US–China great power lens: they are “good news” for China and “bad news” for the United States and the West (Jaipragas 2021; Zawacki 2022; Punongbayan 2022; Thongnoi 2023).

This article begins from the assumption that the relationship between domestic politics and foreign policy attitudes in many Southeast Asian countries is considerably more nuanced than this US–China zero-sum lens might suggest, especially when the wider population is considered. Our focus here is on Thailand: a long-standing American ally that, like many of its Southeast Asian neighbors, has moved closer to China over the past twenty years. Driven by its deepening autocratization after the 2014 military coup, Thailand’s tilt to China raised

alarm bells in the West, stoking fears of waning American influence (Busbarat 2024, 137; Zawacki 2022; Han 2022, 190–193; Detsch 2022).

We move beyond the elite level to study domestic political leanings and foreign policy attitudes of Thai citizens. First, do Thais “prefer” China or the United States? Second, are these preferences related to their domestic political leanings? In other words, to what extent are politically conservative Thais more sympathetic to China, and how far are politically liberal Thais more sympathetic to the United States and other western countries? Or do citizens’ preferences for either China or the United States have relatively little to do with domestic political leanings? We focus on Thai citizens’ foreign policy preferences because wider academic literature shows that public attitudes towards foreign powers can shape elite behaviors even in autocracies (Hyde and Saunders 2020; Weeks 2008; Weiss 2014), while several recent writings on Thailand point to a possible gap between popular and elite attitudes to China (Han 2022, 195–96; Temby 2021; Cogan 2021).

Combining international relations and critical geopolitics literature with data from a new public opinion survey, we show that the link between domestic political preferences of Thai citizens and their attitudes towards the United States and China is weak. While we find some relationship between liberal domestic political leanings and sympathy for America, conservative domestic political leanings do not automatically translate into support for China. Our findings have important implications for academic scholarship and for diplomatic, foreign policy and defense practitioners, extending well beyond the specifics of the Thai case. First, we demonstrate the need to look past political leanings and preferences of elites to better understand the often-complex relations between domestic political views and foreign policy attitudes held by ordinary citizens, in the countries and regions that are central to the US–China rivalry. Second, we show that citizens’ preferences for aligning with the United States or China may have relatively little to do with their domestic political attitudes towards democracy. This points to more pragmatic underpinnings of citizen foreign policy preferences. And third, we demonstrate that policymakers and journalists reading countries’ domestic political developments through the US–China great power lens may result in obfuscations, confusions, and misunderstandings of their complexities. In other words, episodes of democratic backsliding and autocratic deepening within countries in these regions might not automatically translate into good news for China and bad news for the United States.

The article proceeds as follows: part one outlines our criticism of the great power lens as a dominant paradigm, drawing on international relations and critical geopolitics scholarship. Part two offers an overview of Thailand’s international relations with China and the United States, while part three discusses our research design and methodology. Parts four, five and six present key survey findings on Thai people’s attitudes towards China, the United States and other foreign powers, views on domestic political issues, and the relationship between the two. Part seven brings these findings together, while part eight concludes with a discussion of broader implications.

The Geopolitics of the US–China Great Power Lens

Viewing the international order through a great power lens is nothing new. Much of the foreign policy decision-making of the Cold War years was colored by this very lens. Rooted in the realist school of international relations, especially the balance of power approach, the

great power lens stresses the importance of geography to foreign policy thinking and practice. This perspective has led to influential geopolitical scripts that, as Ó Tuathail and Agnew (1992, 192; also see Ó Tuathail 1999, 107) argued, “spatialize international politics in such a way as to represent it as a ‘world’ characterized by particular types of places, peoples and dramas.” Far from being well-grounded in empirical realities, these geopolitical scripts are infused with deeply politicized forms of knowledge that tend to divide the world along simplistic and often binary lines and narratives (Ó Tuathail and Agnew 1992, 192). Once Cold War categories lost their salience, the struggle between democracy and authoritarianism came to dominate most post-Cold War geopolitical scripts. Koch argues that the democracy–authoritarianism binary has become the “hegemonic geopolitical imagery” of today (Koch 2019, 911), often coloring foreign policy thinking and behavior in the West (Koch 2019, 918–21). The result is a fear of authoritarian expansion that poses an existential threat to the liberal international order (LIO).

China’s international rise, which was spurred by rapid economic growth and integration into the global capitalist system following Deng Xiaoping’s economic reforms of the late 1970s, has come to be seen as the biggest threat to the LIO. This was not always the case. Under Deng’s leadership and that of his two successors, Jiang Zemin and Hu Jintao, the Communist Party emphasized the country’s benign re-emergence on the international scene, highlighting caution and an eagerness for cooperation – what Hu termed “peaceful rise” (De Graaf and van Apeldoorn 2018, 117; Nathan 2021, 389). This changed with the elevation of Xi Jinping in 2012. Emboldened by China’s ever-increasing economic and military might, Xi adopted a more assertive foreign policy strategy, focused on developing the country’s security alongside its global political and economic clout. Under his leadership, China is no longer a modest international “rule-taker” but rather an increasingly pro-active “rule-shaper” that recognizes its power and asserts its interests (De Graaf and van Apeldoorn 2018, 118; Brown 2018). In this context, “China’s failure to move toward democracy has been possibly the greatest disappointment for proponents of the LIO” (Glaser 2019, 65).

China has not only refused to adopt the key LIO principles, but it has also started to challenge them. Xi criticizes the dominance of the West, particularly the United States, in global politics; and demands a stronger role for the Global South in a new multilateral order. He has positioned China as an advocate for the Global South in signature initiatives such as the Belt and Road Initiative, the “community of shared destiny” or the Global Security Initiative, and through China’s active engagement in the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China and South Africa) group.¹ There is still no explicit blueprint for an alternative Chinese-led mode of global governance, which Ogden terms a “China-centric authoritarian international order” (Ogden 2022, 3). China also employs a Cold War 2.0 rhetoric, although Beijing holds the United States exclusively responsible for the threatened bifurcation of the international system (Pang 2023). As a result, the official views of both the United States and China, but also of many journalists, foreign policy and defense practitioners contribute to the return of the great power lens.

The US–China great power lens is a product of the hegemonic geopolitical imagery of the democratic West–authoritarian East binary. Such thinking is prevalent among western

¹ Egypt, Ethiopia, Iran, Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates will become BRICS members in 2024. Argentina’s new President Javier Milei withdrew Buenos Aires’ application to join the grouping.

“intellectuals [and practitioners] of statecraft” (Ó Tuathail and Agnew 1992, 193), and has influenced academic writing on global affairs (Kroenig 2020; Mearsheimer 2019; Owen 2021; Brands 2018). For example, in 2019 Mearsheimer (2019) predicted that “there are likely to be Chinese-led and U.S.-led bounded orders” combining economic and security elements. Similarly, in a 2021 article, Owen (2021) argues for the emergence of two international orders – one centered on the liberal West and the other on the authoritarian East, represented by the United States and China respectively. While in both Mearsheimer and Owen’s geopolitical imaginations, these orders could co-exist, they offer limited space for real-world nuance and complexity, reproducing the great power lens script without challenging its dominance. In the sections below, we challenge these geopolitical scripts by using the example of Thailand and examining the extent to which domestic political attitudes of Thai citizens map onto US–China rivalries.

Thailand’s relations with China and the United States

Thailand has a history of strong bilateral relations with the United States. Long-reigning King Bhumibol (Rama IX, r. 1946–2016) was born in Cambridge, Massachusetts, while Thailand served as a crucial American regional ally during the Vietnam War, and was granted Major Non-NATO Ally status by President George W. Bush in 2003. Yet Thailand was not a classic American ally: it was never formally colonized by European powers, and has long proved adept at playing off larger rivals against one another. For example, during the Cold War, Thailand was seen as part of the geopolitical “West”, yet since the early 1970s it also worked towards a gradual rapprochement with China while maintaining its formal American alliance (Wongsurawat 2019, 140; Phillips 2020, 426–28; Busbarat 2016a). Over the past four decades, Thai officials have increasingly described Sino-Thai relations in familial terms, presenting the two countries as “brothers” (Busbarat 2016b). Most of Thailand’s elite has at least some Chinese ancestry. As China embraced capitalism from the early 1980s, Sino-Thai tycoons were among the first major international investors. Some of them entered Thai politics, further strengthening Thailand’s economic and political relations with China, especially following the 1997 Asian financial crisis.

Thailand’s Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn received the Medal of Friendship from Xi Jinping in September 2019, the highest state award bestowed upon foreigners by the People’s Republic of China (PRC). Sirindhorn has made nearly 50 visits to China, has studied Chinese language and culture, and has written thirteen travel memoirs about China and translated thirteen literary works from Chinese into Thai (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People’s Republic of China 2022). Her second state visit to China in April 1990, less than a year after the Tiananmen Square massacre, was a key moment in the establishment of a “special [Sino-Thai] friendship” (Wongsurawat 2022). Newly appointed Thai leader Srettha Thavasin made Beijing the destination for his first official prime ministerial visit beyond ASEAN in October 2023, a detail mentioned by Xi Jinping in his welcome speech (Embassy of People’s Republic of China in Singapore 2023).

Latterly, military collaboration between China and Thailand has also increased: the two countries have ramped up their joint military exercises, Thailand has increased its arms procurements from China, and a large number of Thai officials have undertaken periods of training or educational exchange in China (Busbarat 2024, 133-136; Storey 2019). Over the past forty years Thailand has carefully cultivated good economic, cultural and political

relations with China, while also maintaining warm ties with America and the West. For example, since ascending the throne in 2016, Thailand's King Vajiralongkorn has yet to take up China's public invitation to make a state visit, although he surprised most observers by attending the coronation of King Charles III in May 2023.

The term 'hedging' has been used to describe the foreign policy behavior of most Southeast Asian states and their regional grouping, ASEAN (Gerstl 2022; Jones and Jenne 2022; Kuik 2021). The key feature of hedging is that states engage closely with both great powers, seeking to maximize the benefits from these relations. At the same time, they aim to mitigate economic and security risks stemming from their close ties with Washington DC and Beijing through pursuing omnidirectional political, economic and security relations with other major and small powers.

Thailand's relations with the United States and China, and its ability to hedge between these two great powers, have been complicated by recent domestic political turbulence. Mass protests in 1992 against an attempt by military officers to assume power through quasi-electoral means led to the relatively progressive 1997 "people's constitution," which strengthened both parliament and the executive (McCargo 2002, 291). But within a few years, Thais became deeply polarized between supporters of powerful prime minister Thaksin Shinawatra, who saw him as the champion of ordinary people, and opponents for whom Thaksin was a self-interested opportunist who failed to show due deference towards the monarchy and the establishment. Massive street protests were staged by "yellow" anti-Thaksin demonstrators in 2006, 2008, and 2013–14 – while pro-Thaksin "red" protestors took to the streets in 2009 and 2010, only to be violently suppressed. The military staged coups in 2006 and 2014, to the great chagrin of the United States and the Western bloc. While the Americans penalized Thailand with sanctions for staging military coups (Chachavalpongpun 2016), China seized the opportunity to strengthen its military and defense ties, and to foster closer relations with the conservative Thai elite. This led to Thailand pivoting ever closer to China, especially in the years following the 2014 military takeover (Busbarat 2024, 133-140; Zawacki 2022, 311-322).

The 2014 coup leaders were able narrowly to "win" the eventual March 2019 election: General Prayuth Chan-ocha retained the premiership through a combination of electoral manipulation and "lawfare," including the court-ordered dissolution of a major opposition party. However, a new wave of student-led mass protests erupted in the second half of 2020, this time calling for reform of the monarchy, a topic previously considered taboo. The 2019 election and the 2020–2021 student-led protests failed to rebalance Thailand's relations with the United States as the civilian–military Prayuth administration continued to lean on China for support in areas of defense, economy, and public health – the latter owing to the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic and the initial mismanagement of the US domestic and international public health crisis response under the Trump administration (Busbarat 2024; Zawacki 2022; Chambers 2022).

Political polarization remained very high as the May 2023 election approached. While its domestic fault lines were relatively clear, how far this polarization mapped onto Thai people's attitudes to China and the United States was much less apparent. Were Thais with conservative domestic political leanings also likely to hold positive views about China? By

the same token, were Thais with politically liberal domestic leanings more likely to look favorably towards the United States?

Research design and methodology

To answer these questions, we use data from a survey of 1184 Thai respondents, conducted as part of a larger survey on public opinion towards China in fifteen Southeast and East Asian countries or territories, commissioned by the project Sinophone Borderlands – Interaction at the Edges.² The only obvious comparator survey addressing similar topics is the above-mentioned annual *The State of Southeast Asia Survey Report* by Singapore’s ISEAS-Yusof Ishak Institute, which solicits views from regional informants in the policy field – academics, think tank staff, researchers, business people, civil society and media practitioners, government officials, and staff of international organizations – as opposed to members of the public. In Southeast Asia, there is no direct equivalent of the Afrobarometer³ – which conducted large-scale representative surveys of publics across the African continent – and while Pew recently surveyed East Asian threat perceptions towards China (Silver et al 2023), their work on Southeast Asia tends to focus on issues related to religion and pluralism.

Our survey differs from the ISEAS survey by exploring public attitudes towards China and the United States, complementing existing data and offering more bottom-up insights. The Thailand data was collected online by a private Bangkok-based polling company between 11 April and 23 June 2022, and covered a representative range of respondents from across the country, from all age groups and a variety of socio-economic backgrounds. The questionnaire consisted of more than 300 data points, including several open-ended questions. Respondents were asked about their attitudes towards foreign countries, policy preferences, views about social and human rights issues, and basic demographics. In Thailand, the survey consisted of 67 questions, including 32 standard public opinion questions on China, the United States, and other great powers used in the 15 surveys conducted across the region, and 10 Thailand-specific questions that we designed to probe respondents’ domestic political attitudes.

The survey included questions about respondents’ perceptions towards China and other countries, their citizens, their foreign policy, influence, economic importance and strength, military strength, cultural attractiveness, and quality of life. It also asked more specific questions such as alignment preferences between the United States and China, Thailand’s cultural similarities with China, changes in the respondent’s perceptions of China, and Thailand’s priorities in its relations with China. Thailand-specific questions probed respondents’ political beliefs, including their views on the student protests and military coups, their perception of the monarchy, and of the coup-leader-turned-Prime Minister, General Prayuth.

² “Sinophone Borderlands – Interaction at the Edges,” was a research project funded by the European Regional Development Fund and led by Palacky University Olomouc from 2018 to 2023 (CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16_019/0000791). The Thailand survey was part of a wider study conducted in fifteen Indo-Pacific countries between April and June 2022. In total, 18,157 people were interviewed. For a summary of the Indo-Pacific surveys, see Richard Turcsányi et al, *Public opinion in the Indo-Pacific: divided on China, cheering for US & EU* (Bratislava: CEIAS. 2022), https://ceias.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Draft-2_FINAL.pdf; for more on the survey project, see <https://sinofon.cz/surveys/>

³ See <https://www.afrobarometer.org/about/what-we-do/>

Most of our Thailand specific-questions used a standard 7-point Likert scale and returned a relatively high percentage of neutral answers, ranging from just below 17 to almost 59 per cent. The average neutral response rate for our Thailand-specific standard Likert scale questions was 28 per cent. Two reasons might help explain the relatively high percentage of neutral answers among our respondents. First, our Thailand-specific questions appeared towards the end of the survey, which has been shown to increase the attraction of no-opinion options (Krosnick et al 2002). Second, the combination of Thailand's repressive political environment and the sensitive nature of our questions might have resulted in a degree of self-censorship among our respondents. As Robinson and Tannenbergs (2019) show self-censorship is quite common when it comes to public opinion surveys in authoritarian regimes.

We employed a range of statistical tests to detect correlations between various dependent and independent variables. Methods such as independent samples T-tests, Chi-Squares tests, and contingency tables were implemented to reveal the most significant and relevant connections between select survey questions and our dependent variables. Once the probable associations were deduced, multiple correlation analyses were used to test each of our independent variables simultaneously against the dependent variable of alignment preference while determining the strength, direction, and statistical significance of each variable pair.

Views on China

Several survey questions sought to elicit the respondents' views about the PRC, sometimes in a comparative framework where China was listed alongside other countries, and sometimes using questions specifically focused on the PRC itself. One of the main comparative questions asked respondents to indicate how positively or negatively they felt about 15 different territories, along with ASEAN and the EU (Figure 1). China received the sixth most negative rating in the resulting table – but was viewed significantly more positively than North Korea, Russia, India and Turkey. Only around 15 per cent of the Thai population viewed China negatively, compared with around 12 per cent of Thais who had a negative view of the United States. The table's main feature is its lack of differentiation: except for North Korea, most Thais viewed all the territories and regional groupings on the list in a positive light. Additional questions about attitudes towards the foreign policies of China, the United States, the EU and Japan (Figure 2), including the extent to which Thailand should align its own foreign policy to these countries, also showed little differentiation between China and the United States (Figure 3).

Figure 1: How positively or negatively do you feel about the following countries and entities?

Figure 2: How positively or negatively do you assess the foreign policy of the following countries and entities?

Figure 3: How closely should Thailand's foreign policy align with the following actors?

Another question on views concerning people of various ethnicities and nationalities showed that respondents held more negative views of various Muslim communities, Indians and Africans than they did towards Chinese from the PRC: the proportion of respondents who viewed PRC Chinese negatively was very similar to the proportion who had negative feelings towards Americans, Taiwanese and Europeans, all between 10 and 15 per cent (Figure 4).

Figure 4: How positively or negatively do you feel about the following groups of people?

A more nuanced picture began to emerge when we drilled down to the level of specific China-related issues (Figure 5). Most respondents felt positively towards China, but around 35 per cent had negative views concerning China’s environmental impact, and just under 30 per cent had concerns about Chinese influence on democracy, China’s military power, and China’s rise: in other words, around a third of respondents were uneasy about China’s stances on environmental, political and military issues. Between 10 and 15 per cent also expressed negative feelings about the Belt and Road Initiative, Chinese investments, the promotion of the Chinese language and culture, and China’s trade, and technology. On balance, respondents had more positive feelings towards China when it came to economic and cultural than security-linked issues.

Figure 5: How positively or negatively do you feel about the following issues?

Despite the COVID-19 pandemic, and the accompanying rise of geopolitical tensions between China and the West, 74 per cent of respondents reported that their view of China had improved over the past three years (Figure 6) – that is, between April–June 2019 and April–June 2022. This is likely due to Thailand receiving pandemic assistance from China, including medical equipment and Covid-19 vaccines (Maude and Fraser 2022, 37–38). Only 15 per cent of respondents said that their view of China had worsened during this period.

Based on these responses, there was little real difference between support for China, and support for the United States, or indeed for any other territory or region listed in the survey, among the Thai population. Thailand was quite unusual in being so positive about all these countries and regions – many of its Southeast Asian neighbors displayed more varied attitudes. Thailand’s respondents had the third most positive feelings towards China among the fifteen countries surveyed (Turcsányi et al 2022, 7).

Figure 6: Has your general view of China become better or worse during the last three years?

Nevertheless, one question told a slightly different story. If forced to choose between aligning with China and aligning with the United States, less than a quarter of respondents would pick China, while 66 per cent would align with the United States (Figure 7).⁴ Evidently, while our respondents liked to equivocate, the great majority preferred the United States to China if they had to choose between the two.

⁴ The definition of “alignment” was left deliberately vague in the question.

Figure 7: If you had to decide between the United States and China, which would you choose to align with?

Views on Domestic Issues

At least since 2006, Thailand’s politics has been highly polarized, along pro-Thaksin and anti-Thaksin lines. This polarization was evidenced by the 2007, 2011, and 2019 election results: pro-Thaksin parties won by a strong margin in the populous North and Northeast regions, while anti-Thaksin, pro-military parties performed best in the south and in parts of Bangkok. A similar pattern of polarization was evident during the referendums held in both 2007 and 2016, to ratify constitutions drafted following military coups. In the 2016 referendum, 61 per cent of voters approved the draft constitution, while 39 per cent rejected it: most of the opposition was concentrated in the North and Northeast (Figure 8). In the 2019 election, explicitly anti-military parties (Pheu Thai and Future Forward) won 39 per cent of the vote, while overtly pro-military parties (Palang Pracharat and the Democrats) secured around 34 per cent of the vote – demonstrating another major split among the electorate, much of it along regional lines (Figure 9).⁵ Data from our survey helps unpack Thailand’s domestic polarization further.

⁵ The highly pragmatic Bhumjaithai Party won 10.33 per cent of the vote.

Figure 8: The 2016 Thai constitutional referendum

Figure 9: The 2019 Thai general election

To understand respondents' voting preferences, one of our key questions concerned future voting intentions in a hypothetical imminent election (Figure 10). The opposition Pheu Thai and Move Forward parties were by far the most popular choices, with combined support of around half of all respondents. However, almost a quarter of respondents claimed to be undecided: in practice, some probably favored pro-military parties, but were reluctant to state this. Nevertheless, the expressed voting preferences of those sampled suggested most respondents were at the more liberal end of the Thai political spectrum: less than 15 per cent openly favored either of the two most conservative parties, Palang Pracharat and the

Democrats, a far lower proportion than the 32 per cent who voted for these parties in 2019. The classification of the Democrat Party as a conservative party here reflects the fact that the Democrats formed part of the Prayuth-led government at the time of the survey in 2022. In the 2023 election, the Democrat vote collapsed to just 2.3 per cent of the party list vote and 5.99 per cent of the constituency vote, not least because many former Democrats, especially upper Southerners switched to the hardcore, Prayuth-supporting United Thai Nation Party instead. In other words, a significant proportion of former Democrats still backed the military leadership of the 2014 coup – though by no means all.

Figure 10: If there were parliamentary elections this weekend, which party would you vote for?

Electoral choices in 2023 proved to be more complicated: several new parties were created after our survey, notably the Prayuth-aligned United Thai Nation Party that split the conservative voter base. In addition, a late 2022 change in the ballot system allowed voters to select two different parties, one at the constituency level and another through a national party list. Nevertheless, our survey returned broadly similar results to the 2023 election, in which Pheu Thai and Move Forward together secured almost 60 per cent of the 500 parliamentary seats. In the 2023 polls it was Move Forward, not Pheu Thai, that enjoyed greatest support. Meanwhile, the three most conservative parties running in the 2023 election (Palang Pracharat, United Thai Nation, and the Democrats) won only 20 per cent of seats in total, with 16.4 per cent of the popular vote – very close to the survey results.

Probing into respondents’ domestic political leanings further, a question on the overall performance of Prayuth Chan-o-cha revealed that most respondents – around 60 per cent – held negative views of the then prime minister, and only around 18 per cent assessed his performance positively (Figure 11). A series of seven questions on contentious domestic political issues produced further revealing answers (Figure 12). Respondents were very divided in their sympathies for the post-2020 student protests, which had called for monarchy reform, constitutional revision, and Prayuth’s removal. Roughly a third of respondents were sympathetic towards the youth-led protests, a third were unsympathetic, and the remainder were neutral. About a quarter of respondents agreed with the need for monarchy reform: while this might seem a low level of support, given the extremely sensitive nature of the topic – and the punitive *lèse-majesté* law which curtails critical public discussion of the monarchy – the percentage of respondents willing to express such critical opinions was striking. The large number of neutral, “neither” responses probably masked a significant degree of

skepticism about the royal institution. Less than half of respondents felt that the monarchy was not in need of reform, and less than 20 per cent strongly held that view.

Figure 11: How positively or negatively do you perceive General Prayuth’s overall performance?

Figure 12: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

A third question on whether the 2017 military-drafted constitution should be completely rewritten attracted support from over 60 per cent of respondents, while less than 15 per cent disagreed. This core demand of the youth-led protestors appeared to command considerable public sympathy. Two other questions demonstrated strong support for progressive political positions: a clear majority (more than 70 per cent) favored electing provincial governors by local people, a reform long resisted by Thailand’s bureaucratic elite. Except in Bangkok, provincial governors are appointed Ministry of Interior officials, who are dispatched from the

capital to oversee the administration of the rest of Thailand in a quasi-colonial fashion. A similar proportion of respondents believed the military should not be allowed to stage any more coups. Only around 6 per cent of respondents felt that future coups ought to be permitted, while over 70 per cent were opposed. This marked a significant decline from the levels of coup sympathy expressed in previous surveys, suggesting that the May 2014 coup was now widely regarded as a bad idea.

Respondent views on Thai coups were echoed by an additional question about how ASEAN should react to the 1 February 2021 military coup in Myanmar (Figure 13): 70 per cent of those surveyed believed ASEAN should demand the return of an elected government there. Although not about Thailand, this response to a closed question suggested that, in principle, over two-thirds of respondents opposed authoritarianism and favored at least some form of democracy.

Figure 13: How should ASEAN respond to the military coup in Myanmar?

Perhaps unsurprisingly, there was also overwhelming support for the idea that people should have the right to free healthcare, suggesting that Thais were very sympathetic to the creation of a welfare state – reflecting the legacy of the first Thaksin government’s 30-baht healthcare scheme – and did not see such policies as examples of cynical populism (Figure 12).

On one crucial issue, however, the respondents held strongly conservative views: fewer than 10 per cent believed that the Muslim-majority southern border provinces – the site of a violent secessionist insurgency since 2004 – should be permitted to rule themselves (Figure 12). Most respondents could not make the leap from embracing elected provincial governors in general, to granting particular regions of Thailand greater autonomy. More research would be needed to tease out the implications here, but the responses suggest a lack of sympathy towards the Muslim-majority deep south by Buddhist Thais from other parts of the country, echoing the more negative views towards Muslim minorities held by Thais (see Figure 4).

Except for the question concerning autonomy for the deep south, most respondents expressed broadly “pro-democratic” views: they were not happy with General Prayuth, they favored opposition parties, opposed military coups, supported elected governors and wanted to see the

2017 constitution extensively revised. They were more divided on support for the student-led protests and the need for monarchical reform. Since Thailand's ruling conservative elite was often aligned with China, we might reasonably expect to find a correlation between those respondents embracing "anti-democratic" domestic positions, and various forms of support and sympathy for China. By the same token, respondents embracing pro-democratic views might be expected to be more positively disposed towards the United States and Europe.

Correlating Domestic Political Views and Attitudes to China and the United States

To examine whether Thai domestic political views correlate with attitudes toward China and the United States, we used the alignment question as our dependent variable because it gave us the clearest indication of the respondents' attitudes to China and the United States. The question also returned a relatively low number of neutral answers (10.1 per cent) compared to the other questions that explored respondents' attitudes to China, the United States and other great powers. The question asked: "If you had to decide between the United States and China, which would you choose to align with?" Respondents had to mark their answers on a standard 7-point Likert scale, with higher values representing a stronger desire to align with America and lower values representing a stronger desire to align with China. Our independent variables consisted of ten domestic political attitudes questions. They included two questions on voting preferences (as in the 2019 election and in the hypothetical poll discussed in the section above) and eight of our Thailand-specific standard 7-point Likert scale questions: two on decentralization (election of provincial governors and southern rule), and one question each on respondents' red-yellow alignment, General Prayuth's performance, monarchy reform, the 2020–2021 student protests, constitutional reform and military coups.

We used Thailand's domestic political polarization as a proxy to classify respondents' answers as either politically conservative or politically liberal. Politically conservative answers to the two voting preference questions comprised respondents' preferences for military-aligned parties (Palang Pracharat, the Democrats, and the Action Coalition for Thailand), conservative parties (Chart Thai Pattana) or ultra-pragmatic parties (Bhumjai Thai). Politically liberal answers to these questions comprised respondents' preferences for explicitly anti-military and/or pro-Thaksin parties (Pheu Thai, Future Forward, Seri Ruam Thai and Prachachart), or new parties with anti-establishment branding that were formed after the 2019 election (Thai Sang Thai). Politically conservative answers to the eight standard Likert scale questions included support for future military coups, positive assessments of General Prayuth's performance, negative views of the 2020–2021 student-led protests, and opposition to Thaksin (yellow alignment), decentralization, reform of the monarchy and the rewriting of the 2017 constitution. By contrast, politically liberal answers included opposition to future military coups, negative assessments of General Prayuth's performance, and positive views of the student protests, decentralization, and reforms of the monarchy and the constitution. Arguably, they may also include support for Thaksin (red alignment). We assigned higher numerical values to politically conservative and lower values to politically liberal answers to the two voting preference questions. Given the differences in the formulation of our standard Likert scale questions, politically conservative answers to the questions on Prayuth's performance, monarchy reform, student protests, and southern autonomy were high-value responses. By contrast, politically conservative answers on red-yellow alignment, constitutional reform, future military coups, and the election of provincial governors were low-value responses.

We then ran a series of statistical tests to examine whether there was any correlation between our dependent variable – Thai respondents’ United States–China alignment preference – and each of our ten independent variables. This was achieved through a multiple correlation analysis; a statistical method used to explore and quantify the relationship between several independent variables and one dependent variable.

Our results showed that most Thai people’s domestic political views correlated with their US–China attitudes, but the nature of these relationships was weak. Figure 14 shows that while those Thais who voted for politically liberal parties in the 2019 election were more likely to align with the United States than those who voted for politically conservative parties, around half of the conservative voters still chose to align with the United States over China. The results for the hypothetical 2022 Thai election were almost identical (Figure 15): Thais with liberal voting choices were more likely to favor the United States, but the conservative voter base was once again divided over its US–China alignment.

Figure 14: 2019 Thai election choices and US-China alignment

Figure 15: Hypothetical 2022 Thai election and US-China alignment

A similar trend is evident with most other independent variables. Figure 16 shows that those Thais who self-identified as more “red”— in other words, supported pro-Thaksin, anti-military stances and were coded as politically liberal – were more likely to choose closer alignment with the United States than those who self-identified as more “yellow”. However, even those Thais who self-identified as more “yellow” – in other words, opposed Thaksin and were coded as politically conservative – did not display a strong preference for aligning with China.

Figure 16: Yellow-versus-red spectrum position and US-China alignment

Politically liberal Thais who supported the rewriting of the 2017 military-drafted constitution (Figure 17), opposed future military coups (Figure 18) and were in favor of electing

provincial governors (Figure 19) were also more likely to choose alignment with the United States over that with China. On the other hand, Thais who viewed Prayuth’s performance more favorably chose closer alignment with China (Figure 20). The same was true for those Thais who did not want to reform the monarchy: they were more likely to align closer with China, but the difference here was marginal, as with the other variables (Figure 21).

Figure 17: Constitutional rewriting and US-China alignment

Figure 18: Thai military coups and US-China alignment

Figure 19: Electing provincial governors and US-China alignment

Figure 20: General Prayuth and US-China alignment

Figure 21: Reforming monarchy and US-China alignment

There was no relationship between respondents' views on southern self-rule and their attitudes to the two great powers (Figure 22). This absence was not surprising given that the southern self-rule question attracted the highest number of conservative responses out of the ten Thailand-specific questions.

Figure 22: Southern self-rule and US-China alignment

A more surprising result was the absence of any relationship between respondents' views on the 2020–2021 student protests and their US–China attitudes (Figure 23). While the student-led protests were primarily a challenge to Thailand's ruling elite, they were also linked with the pan-Asian #MilkTeaAlliance – an online movement that started as an anti-Chinese campaign by young Twitter users in Thailand, Hong Kong and Taiwan, but soon gained a broader reputation for challenging authoritarianism across Asia (McCargo 2021; Schaffar and Wongratanawin 2021; Sombatpoonsiri 2021).

Figure 23: Student-led protests and US-China alignment

Discussion

For the most part, our survey results show that Thais view both China and the United States very favorably, indicating a lack of differentiation along the hegemonic US–China great power axis. Thais are geopolitically upbeat, holding very favorable views of Europe and Japan as well. Japan also scores very positively with ASEAN elite informants in the ISEAS surveys. North Korea was one of the few countries that inspired much negative sentiment, but even Pyongyang was viewed positively by more than half of our respondents. Thais do not apparently see themselves as caught up in global power struggles, let alone a zero-sum game between America and China, tending to equivocate in their assessments of the two major powers in the region.

Thais viewed China favorably across a wide range of areas. Around 80 per cent held positive views of China in general – numbers very similar to those for the United States, UK, Taiwan, France, Germany, the EU, Australia, Singapore, Japan and ASEAN – and broadly saw China's foreign policy positively. Around 65 per cent of respondents felt that Thailand's foreign policy should align with China's completely or to a significant extent, and similar levels of approval were expressed regarding China's rise, the Belt and Road initiative, investments, culture, trade and technology. The great majority of respondents stated that their perceptions of China had improved over the last three years.

Only in the one question where respondents were forced to choose between alignment with China and the United States did a distinct perception gap emerge, revealing a marked preference for America – favored by 63 per cent of respondents, versus 24 per cent who preferred China.

The apparent lack of differentiation in Thai people's attitudes towards China and the United States was in a stark contrast to domestic polarization. Our survey clearly showed that Thais hold highly polarized political opinions on a wide range of topics, as evidenced by the two questions concerning voting intentions, and several of our questions on contentious domestic issues. The survey demonstrated a strong groundswell of support for the opposition Pheu Thai and Move Forward parties, a trend that was abundantly validated by the results of the May 2023 elections held a year after our survey was conducted. But the survey also showed significant residual support for conservative positions on fraught issues such as decentralizing power to the south, and reform of the monarchy.

Despite the existence of a clear split between pro-America and pro-China respondents when forced to choose between the two great powers, and between those with politically liberal domestic orientations versus those of conservative leanings, our findings suggest that Thai people's domestic political attitudes do not map neatly on the US–China great power lens. While there is some relationship between a preference for liberal domestic stances and sympathy for the United States, a significant proportion of politically conservative Thais also prefer America. In other words, many conservatives are happy to align with the wider democratic world internationally, whilst accepting authoritarian trends inside Thailand. This apparent contradiction suggests that Thai people's attitudes to China and the United States are motivated by more pragmatic concerns than their domestic political views. It can also partly be examined by the ambiguous domestic and external stances of parties such as the Democrats. Thailand's economic growth is heavily dependent on exports, foreign direct investment, and tourism (World Bank 2022), while its external security hinges on alliances with larger powers (Han 2022, 184). As our survey results show, most Thais would clearly prefer maintaining good relations with all their neighbors, as well as with all their current and potential trade partners and security allies, indicating a strong preference for a balanced foreign policy approach.

Conclusion

As the US–China rivalry discourse continues to amplify, it is important that the domestic politics of countries in Southeast Asia and other key geostrategic regions for the United States become much better understood. This has important implications for foreign and defense policy making – as well as the broader democracy support programs targeted at these regions – in Washington DC and the West more generally. If American think tankers misunderstand the domestic politics of countries like Thailand, US diplomatic and defense responses might exacerbate rather than defuse tensions with Beijing at a time of increased international contestation.

Thailand's domestic politics is not a zero-sum geopolitical game, with Western-oriented democrats on one side and China-oriented authoritarians on the other. The Thai case illustrates the limitations of great power-centered realism as an explanatory lens for reading Southeast Asia's messy and contentious domestic political orders. Our 2022 nationally representative survey of 1184 ordinary Thai respondents demonstrates that irrespective of their domestic political preferences, most Thais prefer to adopt a middle course between competing global and regional powers, viewing both China and the United States in a broadly positive light. Ours is the first survey directly to ask ordinary Thai voters their views on sensitive issues such as monarchy reform, the 2020 protests, and the decentralization of

power. It is also unique in linking respondent's views on domestic politics to their geopolitical perspectives. As such, it breaks important new analytical ground.

As with many of its neighbors, Thailand's politics is driven by a wide range of factors that complicate reductionist interpretations. In the Thai case, these include the interventionist roles of the all-important monarchy and the coup-happy military; as well as the extremely dynamic and fluid nature of both the party system and voter preferences. When all these factors affect foreign policy attitudes, the result, unsurprisingly, is not a neat distinction between pro-America democrats and pro-China autocrats, but rather what we might term "domestic hedging" on the part of the ordinary Thai population.

This article makes an important contribution to debates about the salience of the great powers in relation to the domestic and comparative politics of Southeast Asia and other regions of geostrategic importance. Despite some misleading international headlines, Thailand's politics are not all about China and its authoritarian models of development, and nor are they largely shaped by democratic agendas set by the United States. Indeed, foreign policy issues were scarcely mentioned during the 2023 Thai general election campaign. Domestic Southeast Asian politics are largely driven by internal factors and local particularities: while some of these features span the democracy-autocracy spectrum, they are mostly unrelated to the international rivalries that so preoccupy the Washington beltway and the headline-writers of American newsrooms. While those rivalries are certainly important in framing the nature of geopolitical dynamics in Southeast Asia, they tell us relatively little about the core issues that underpin voting choices, street protests, and regime change – including at times support for military coups – and how these translate into ordinary people's views of world politics.

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